

EFFECTIVENESS OF USING THE ZOOM PLATFORM IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN MEDICAL AND FUNDAMENTAL SCIENCES

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Annotation. The article discusses the features of using **the Zoom platform** in the educational process in medical and fundamental sciences. The purpose of the study is to assess the effectiveness of using this platform for organizing distance learning. Its functionality is analyzed, including video conferencing, demonstration of educational materials, use of an interactive whiteboard, organization of group work in session halls, as well as the functions of recording classes and monitoring students' knowledge. Special attention is paid to the advantages of the platform, such as a stable connection, simplicity of the interface, accessibility from various devices and a high level of interactivity.

The results of the analysis show that the use of Zoom helps to improve the quality of the educational process, provides flexibility in the organization of training sessions and expands the possibilities of interaction between teachers and students. The platform can be considered as an effective tool for implementing modern forms of distance learning, especially relevant in the context of limitations of the full-time educational process.

Keywords: Zoom platform, provider, online class, browser, conference, identification number.

TIBBIY VA FUNDAMENTAL FANLARDA TA'LIM JARAYONIDA ZOOM PLATFORMASIDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARALARI TOSHKENT XALQARO UNIVERSITETI SAMARQAND FILIALI

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Tibbiyot va fundamental fanlar kafedrasida tibbiyot fanlari nomzodi,
dotsent v.b.

Annotatsiya: ushbu maqola tibbiyot va fundamental fanlar bo'yicha ta'lim sharoitlarida Zoom platformasidan foydalanishni o'rganadi. Tadqiqotning maqsadi masofaviy ta'limni tashkil etish uchun ushbu platformadan foydalanish samaradorligini baholashdan iborat. Uning funksional imkoniyatlari, jumladan, videokonferens-aloqa, o'quv materiallarini namoyish etish, interfaol doskadan foydalanish, mashg'ulot xonalarida guruh ishini tashkil etish, shuningdek, darslarni yozib olish va

talabalar bilimini nazorat qilish funksiyalari tahlil qilingan. Maqolada platformaning barqaror ulanish, oddiy interfeys, turli qurilmalardan foydalanish imkoniyati va yuqori darajadagi interaktivlik kabi afzalliklariga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Tahlil natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, Zoom dasturidan foydalanish o'quv jarayoni sifatini oshiradi, o'quv faoliyatini tashkil etishda moslashuvchanlikni ta'minlaydi, o'qituvchi va talabalar o'rtasidagi o'zaro hamkorlik imkoniyatlarini kengaytiradi. Platformani masofaviy ta'limning zamonaviy shakllarini amalga oshirishning samarali vositasi deb hisoblash mumkin, bu ayniqsa ta'lim jarayoniga cheklovlar sharoitida dolzarbdir.

Kalit so'zlar: Zoom platformasi, provayder, onlayn sinf, brauzer, konferentsiya, identifikatsiya raqami.

**ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ПЛАТФОРМЫ
ZOOM В ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОМ ПРОЦЕССЕ В
МЕДИЦИНСКИХ И ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ НАУКАХ
ТАШКЕНТСКИЙ МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ УНИВЕРСИТЕТ
ФИЛИАЛ В САМАРКАНДЕ**

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Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются особенности использования платформы Zoom в образовательном процессе в области медицинских и фундаментальных наук. Цель исследования – оценить эффективность использования данной платформы для организации дистанционного обучения. Анализируются ее функциональные возможности, в том числе видеоконференцсвязь, демонстрация учебных материалов, использование интерактивной доски, организация групповой работы в сессионных залах, а также функции записи занятий и контроля знаний студентов. Особое внимание уделяется преимуществам платформы, таким как стабильное соединение, простота интерфейса, доступность с различных устройств и высокий уровень интерактивности. Результаты анализа показывают, что использование Zoom способствует повышению качества образовательного процесса, обеспечивает гибкость в организации учебных занятий и расширяет возможности взаимодействия между преподавателями и студентами. Платформа может рассматриваться как эффективный инструмент для реализации современных форм дистанционного обучения, что особенно актуально в условиях ограничений очного образовательного процесса.

Ключевые слова: платформа Zoom, провайдер, онлайн-класс, браузер, конференция, идентификационный номер.

Relevance of the topic. In the modern educational process, the use of digital technologies and distance learning forms is becoming increasingly important. This need was particularly acute during the period of quarantine restrictions, when traditional forms of face-to-face interaction between teachers and students were difficult or impossible. Basic medical sciences (anatomy, histology, physiology, etc.) occupy a key place in the system of medical education, as they form the basis for further study of clinical disciplines. Their teaching requires not only a high-quality presentation of theoretical material, but also the use of interactive methods that ensure the active involvement of students in the educational process. **The Zoom platform**, which has a wide range of functions for organizing video conferences, interactive classes and knowledge control, is a promising tool for implementing the educational process in a remote format. Studying the effectiveness of its application in teaching basic medical sciences is an urgent task, as it allows us to justify the feasibility of integrating modern digital technologies into the training of future specialists in the field of medicine.

In recent years, the world's educational practice has seen the active introduction of digital technologies and distance learning. According to a number of studies, online platforms provide new opportunities for improving the accessibility and quality of the educational process (Anderson, 2019; Bates, 2020). The use of видеоконференц video conferencing allows you to implement not only traditional lectures, but also interactive forms of learning, including group discussions, practical tasks and knowledge control.

These technologies are particularly important in medical education, where fundamental disciplines such as anatomy, histology and physiology require a high level of visualization of educational material and constant interaction between the teacher and students (Prober & Khan, 2013; Cook et al., 2017). A number of authors note that the integration of digital platforms into the teaching of these disciplines contributes to the formation of students' analytical thinking, the development of independent work skills and the increase of motivation for learning (Gupta et al., 2020).

The Zoom platform stands out among other distance learning systems due to its simple interface, stable connectivity, and broad functionality. Recent studies have emphasized that Zoom provides opportunities for organizing group work (session halls), conducting interactive classes using a virtual whiteboard, recording and subsequent analysis of training sessions (Singh et al., 2021; Mukhtar et al., 2020). In addition, the presence of a joint screen demonstration and control transfer function ensures a high level of student engagement.

Thus, the literature analysis shows that the use of Zoom in the educational process corresponds to current trends in the development of medical education and can be an effective tool for teaching medical and fundamental sciences. However, despite a significant number of papers devoted to general issues of distance learning, there are still not enough studies aimed at evaluating the effectiveness of using Zoom specifically in teaching fundamental medical disciplines. This determines the need for further research in this area.

Currently, in the practice of distance education, along with traditionally used platforms, such as **Skype**, the Zoom system is becoming increasingly widespread. This platform is designed for organizing video conferences, online meetings, and interactive educational sessions. One of its key advantages is the simplicity of the interface and intuitive functionality, which allows you to effectively use the program in various settings, including the educational process in medical universities.

Zoom provides a stable connection, the ability to demonstrate training materials, conduct group discussions, record classes and then analyze them. These functional features make the platform a promising tool for implementing modern forms of distance learning, in particular in the study of medical and fundamental disciplines. The software is available for free download on the developer's official website (<https://zoom.us/download>), and detailed installation and operating instructions are provided for users. After downloading **the Zoom software**, the user installs it on a personal computer and is activated via email. To organize a conference, you need to create an account, and even the basic (free) version provides the ability to hold video conferences lasting up to 40 minutes.

The platform's functionality makes it a convenient tool for both individual and group classes. Access to the conference is possible from various devices – a personal computer, smartphone or tablet. Participants can be connected via an individual link or conference ID. Additionally, you can pre-schedule online activities, as well as generate duplicate links, which allows you to use the same ID for regular classes at a set time.

Analysis of the Zoom platform functionality allows us to identify a number of advantages that ensure its effectiveness in organizing distance learning, including when teaching medical and fundamental disciplines:

- **high connection stability.** Practical application shows that the platform is reliable and free from technical failures, which is especially important when conducting online classes.

- **advanced audio and video communication tools.** The conference organizer has the ability to manage the audio and video signal

of participants, including the activation and deactivation of microphones, as well as the restriction or requirement to enable video communication;

- **screen demonstration function.** The platform provides for broadcasting both the entire screen and individual program windows (for example, a browser), while it is possible to control the soundtrack and pause the demo. Access to this function can be restricted only by the organizer or granted to all participants.

- **interactive whiteboard.** The built-in tool allows you to quickly switch between the screen demonstration and visualization modes of information on the blackboard, which expands the teacher's didactic capabilities.

- **chat with advanced features.** Participants can exchange text messages and files with the entire group, as well as in an individual format. Additionally, the ability to automatically or manually save the history of correspondence is implemented.

- **record classes.** The platform supports local and cloud-based conference recording. The user can pre-configure automatic recording or manage the process manually, which facilitates subsequent analysis of the training material.

- **ability to assign a co-organizer.** The organizer can delegate some of the powers to another user, thereby ensuring joint management of the educational process (turning microphones on and off, renaming participants, distributing them to rooms, etc.).

Thus, the combination of these functions makes the Zoom platform an optimal tool for implementing interactive distance learning and ensures a high level of student involvement in the educational process.

One of the most important features **of the Zoom platform**, which contributes to improving the effectiveness of the educational process, is the ability to divide students into pairs and small groups. This tool allows you to create so-called session halls (mini-conferences), where students can interact only with each other, which simulates working in small groups during traditional face-to-face classes. The number of session halls is determined by the teacher, and the distribution of students can be carried out both automatically and manually. The organizer retains control over the process: it can move between halls, check the progress of tasks, and also, if necessary, transfer participants from one group to another.

An additional advantage of the platform is the presence **of a virtual background function**, which makes it possible to form a specific visual environment and contributes to a more comfortable perception of educational material.

In addition, Zoom is equipped **with an on-screen collaborative annotation tool** that allows you to select, draw, comment or erase

elements of the displayed material. This feature is available to both teachers and students, but for the latter, it may be restricted in the settings. This ensures not only a variable presentation of information, but also a high level of interactivity when studying educational material.

During online classes, the **Zoom platform** provides a screen demonstration function that allows the teacher to broadcast a variety of educational materials (presentations, video files, diagrams, images, etc.) to students with simultaneous oral comments. Additionally, the ability to transfer mouse and keyboard control to conference participants is implemented. This expands the teacher's didactic capabilities: the student can perform a number of actions on the organizer's computer, including scrolling through presentation slides, working with interactive applications, attaching images, and other operations.

A limitation of the platform is that students do not have the ability to move objects on the virtual whiteboard (unlike specialized services, such as Realtimeboard), but access to the teacher's screen management compensates for this disadvantage. When this feature is activated, a request appears on the organizer's screen, and if both users agree, they will have access to mouse and keyboard controls, while the speaker will have priority.

The student assessment process can be integrated using the Zoom platform: knowledge control is carried out both through testing in a modular system and based on student activity during online classes. An important tool for analyzing and subsequent use of training materials is the ability to record conferences on the user's device or in cloud storage, which ensures that the course of the lesson is saved and further processed.

Conclusion. The Zoom platform can be considered as one of the most convenient and effective solutions for organizing distance learning in medical education. Its functionality ensures that lectures, seminars and practical classes are held at a convenient time for teachers and students, as well as contributes to maintaining a high level of interactivity.

Using Zoom allows you not only to broadcast educational material, but also to implement such elements of the educational process as knowledge control, organization of discussions and question-and-answer sessions, which is especially important in the conditions of distance learning, including the period of quarantine restrictions.

Thus, the Zoom platform has established itself as a modern and reliable tool for teaching medical and fundamental disciplines, combining accessibility, ease of use and a wide range of didactic capabilities. Its application helps to improve the quality of the educational process and expand opportunities for interactive interaction between teachers and students.

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